

ROMI - WP3
Understanding the
social-ecological system

Deliverable 5
Vulnerability against climate change

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1 Data

1.1 Observations

Automatic weather station observations of air temperature and precipitation in the region are used within the gridded observational dataset SPARTACUS (Hiebl and Frey, 2016 and 2018). We employ this dataset to illustrate the past development of the regional climate.

Daily manual observations of snow depth are available for the location Lackenhof. This long time-series allow us to investigate changes and variations in the snow cover, since 1896.

1.2 Regional Climate Models

Considering future developments of the regional climate, the Austrian national reference scenario dataset ÖKS15 (Chimani et al., 2016) and STARC-Impact is used. The ensemble of regional climate model (RSM) simulations are forced by CMIP5 global climate models. ÖKS15 and Starc-Impact offer three different representative concentration pathways (RCP) RCP8.5, RCP4.5 and RCP2.6. In this analysis we only utilize the low emission scenario RCP2.6 and the business-as-usual scenario RCP8.5 in order to reduce the analysis output and complexity, while still encompass possible future developments.

For the RCP8.5, 16 distinct model runs are available, while there are 8 for RCP2.6. The Global climate model simulations are downscaled and biascorrected using an optimized quantile mapping approach (Switanek et al., 2017), preserving the initial climate change.

Central to this study are recent and near future developments relate to climate change, ensuring relevance for local stakeholders within imminent planning horizons. Therefore, the following analysis focuses on the recent climate period (1991-2020) and the near future (2021-2050). Nonetheless, we also present climate predictions on longer timescales (up to 2100) for temperature and precipitation for context.

It is worth noting, that all scenarios are biascorrected individually, hence, there can also be differences between the different RCMs during the historical runs (encompassing the period 1971-2005). Within the climate period 1991-2020, differences in the RCM are further expected as they already start to diverge due to their different scenario-dependent radiation forcings.

1.3 Study Domain

The gridded datasets are aggregated within the boundaries of the four municipalities of Annaberg, Puchenstuben, Gaming and Mitterbach and referred to in this report as the Ötscher region.

2 Overview of Historic Climate

2.1 Air Temperature

The examination of winter temperatures (Figure 1, top left) discloses a long-term increasing trend from 1961 to the present, characterized by alternating cooler and warmer phases in a wave-like pattern. A significant upswing is observed towards the end of the 1980s, followed by a cooling phase until around 2010. During this cooling period, temperatures returned to levels comparable to those before 1989. Notably, recent years have witnessed a resurgence of warmer winters, aligning with a global trend of above-average winter temperatures. The data also highlights the substantial year-to-year variability in winter temperatures.

The analysis of summer air temperatures (Figure 1, top right) indicates a marked rise since the early 1980s, with an increase ranging between 2°C and 3°C compared to the long-term average for the period 1961 to 1990. This warming trend is also observable, albeit to a lesser extent, in spring, and recent years show a significant warming trend in autumn as well. Overall, the data demonstrates a consistent increase in air temperatures across all seasons since 1961, with the most substantial changes occurring since the 1980s. This is further evidenced by positive deviations in the comparison of the normal climate period from 1961 to 1990, depicted in red, indicating temperatures above the average for that period.

Figure 1: Area-mean Air Temperature time-series and anomalies for the four seasons (winter: top left, summer: top right, spring: lower left, autumn: lower right). The analysis is based on the gridded observational data-set SPARTACUS.

2.2 Precipitation

The examination of seasonal precipitation sums over the study area, as depicted in Figure 2, reveals a notable absence of a clear long-term trend. Instead, the data illustrates a pattern of alternating wet and dry periods without a discernible overall trajectory. Specifically, winter precipitation sums exhibit variability, with periods of below-average precipitation observed in the 1990s and more recently. Unlike air temperature, precipitation sums display a significantly higher level of year-to-year and multi-year variability. This suggests that precipitation patterns are subject to fluctuations over shorter time scales, contributing to the absence of a pronounced long-term trend in the dataset.

Figure 2: Area-mean time-series and anomalies of precipitation sum for the four seasons (winter: top left, summer: top right, spring: lower left, autumn: lower right). The analysis is based on the gridded observational data-set SPARTACUS.

2.3 Snow Cover

The analysis of snow cover duration, specifically measured as the number of days with a snow depth of ≥ 10 cm at the Lackenhof station at 809 m a.s.l. (Figure 3), provides insightful observations into the temporal patterns of snow presence in the region. The data illustrates marked variations in snow cover duration, ranging between 35 and 200 days. Over the last two decades, a noticeable decline in snow cover duration is evident. However, it's noteworthy that this recent decline does not surpass previously observed periods of decline, such as the one between 1905 and 1920. This historical context is crucial for understanding that the current trend is not unprecedented and has historical analogs. The observed decrease in snow cover duration in the last 20 years is attributed to milder and notably drier winters.

Figure 3: Time-series of snow cover duration from manual observations for the station Lackenhof. Bold line is a smoothed representation (Gauß Filter)

3 Climate Change Projections

3.1 Temperature

Figure 4: Moving average over shifting horizon (MASH) analysis of air temperature for the period 1971–2100 for Ötscher Region. The daily air temperature time series is averaged over the horizontal and vertical time axis using a 5 year and 31-day moving window, respectively.

The large-scale weather conditions and the associated distribution of temperature and precipitation play an important role in climate change. Temperature and precipitation time series are often characterized by strong seasonal and annual variability. To address this variability, the Moving Average over Shifting Horizon (MASH) analysis is employed as a filtering method, smoothing fluctuations in two dimensions: over the same days in consecutive years and over consecutive days in the same year. This approach helps reduce high-frequency year-to-year variability and provides a clearer picture of long-term trends.

The temperature time series are averaged over 31 days and 5 years, aiming to capture changes in a more stable manner. The results of the MASH analysis offer valuable insights

into the changes in temperature and precipitation, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of climate patterns.

Figure 4 presents a qualitative impression of the anticipated mean air temperature changes in the Ötscher region under the emission scenarios RCP2.6 (top) and RCP8.5 (bottom) until the end of the 21st century. Both scenarios project an increase in temperature (increase highlighted by red shaded areas, decrease in blue shaded areas). This impact is observed across all months considered. The projections align until the middle of the 21st century due to the longevity of greenhouse gases and the inertia of the climate system. Notably, from 2050 onwards, RCP8.5 foresees a substantial temperature increase in all months, indicating the delayed response of climate policy measures.

Compared to the baseline period of 1991-2020, both scenarios predict a further increase in mean annual air temperature for the near future (2021-2050) independent of altitude. Specifically, the projections suggest an increase of +0.6°C for RCP 2.6 and +0.84°C for RCP 8.5.

Figure 5: Mean seasonal air temperature for the Ötscher Region for the ÖKS 15 regional climate scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5. Left column of sub-figures shows time-series of smoothed ensemble statistics (median, 10th and 90th percentile), right column shows the ensemble distribution of mean values over three different climate periods.

Figure 6: Mean annual air temperature for the Ötscher Region for the ÖKS 15 regional climate scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5. Left column of sub-figures shows time-series of smoothed ensemble statistics (median, 10th and 90th percentile), right column shows the ensemble distribution of mean values over three different periods. Values are reported for two elevation ranges.

Table 3.1: Median (min | max) values of ÖKS15 model ensemble for mean annual air temperature (°C) over the period 1991-2020 and the change signal in the period 2021-2050 over two elevation ranges.

RCP	elevation	1991-2020	Δ in 2021-2050
RCP2.6	< 1000 m asl	7.10 (6.96 7.47)	+0.6 (+0.34 +1.17)
	≥ 1000 m asl	5.54 (5.42 5.93)	+0.6 (+0.35 +1.16)
RCP8.5	< 1000 m asl	7.29 (6.92 7.80)	+0.84 (+0.23 +1.4)
	≥ 1000 m asl	5.74 (5.37 6.23)	+0.84 (+0.25 +1.39)

3.2 Precipitation

Figure 7: Moving average over shifting horizon (MASH) analysis of precipitation for the period 1971–2100 for Ötscher Region. The daily precipitation time series is accumulated over the horizontal and vertical time axis using a 5 year and 31-day moving window, respectively.

Figure 7 shows the results of the precipitation MASH analysis. Similarly to Figure 4, daily precipitation sums are summed over 31 days and averaged over 5 years. The climate scenarios are very similar. Dry and wet periods alternate; there is no clear trend (as with temperature) towards more or less precipitation by the end of the 21st century. This can be explained by the fact that precipitation has a very large spatial and temporal variability.

Figure 8: Annual precipitation sum in the Ötscher Region for the ÖKS 15 regional climate scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5. Left column of sub-figures shows time-series of smoothed ensemble statistics (median, 10th and 90th percentile), right column shows the ensemble distribution of mean values over three different periods. Values are reported for two elevation ranges.

Comparing annual precipitation sums averaged over the period 1991-2020 and 2021-2050, reveals a slight increase in precipitation (Table 3.2) of about +4%.

Table 3.2: Median (min | max) values of ÖKS15 model ensemble for annual precipitation sum (mm) over the period 1991-2020 and the change signal in the period 2021-2050 over two elevation ranges.

RCP	elevation	1991-2020	Δ in 2021-2050
RCP2.6	< 1000 m asl	1627.10 (1524.48 1714.32)	+67.36 (-96.15 +150.03)
	≥ 1000 m asl	1827.52 (1711.63 1927.85)	+76.92 (-102.75 +175.22)
RCP8.5	< 1000 m asl	1621.67 (1436.63 1680.48)	+62.23 (-30.13 +227.57)
	≥ 1000 m asl	1817.51 (1613.23 1881.40)	+73.03 (-38.11 +251.49)

4 Effect of Climate Change Projections

The effect of a changing climate on various fields can be analysed based on different indicators, derived from temperature and precipitation projections. See Appendix for details and definition of these indicators.

4.1 Heat

Figure 9 shows the annual number of hot days, i.e. the number of days where the maximum air temperature is over 30°C. Both scenarios show an increase in the number of hot days between the two climate periods with a median change signal of +1.2 days for RCP 2.6 and +2.1 days for RCP 8.5 for elevations under 1000 m (Table 4.1). The absolute values, however, are still far from being critical e.g. for human health (for comparison, in Vienna 21 hot days are predicted in 2021-2050, on average).

Figure 9: Annual number of hot days ($T_{max} \geq 30^{\circ}\text{C}$) in the Ötscher Region for the ÖKS 15 regional climate scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5. Left column of sub-figures shows time-series of smoothed ensemble statistics (median, 10th and 90th percentile), right column shows the ensemble distribution of mean values over two different periods. Values are reported for two elevation ranges.

Table 4.1: Median (min | max) values of ÖKS15 model ensemble for annual number of hot days ($T_{max} \geq 30^{\circ}\text{C}$) over the period 1991-2020 and the change signal in the period 2021-2050 over two elevation ranges

RCP	elevation	1991-2020	Δ in 2021-2050
RCP2.6	< 1000 m asl	3.42 (2.55 4.92)	+1.24 (+0.34 +3.54)
	\geq 1000 m asl	0.39 (0.16 0.62)	+0.4 (-0.06 +0.92)
RCP8.5	< 1000 m asl	3.56 (2.80 5.71)	+2.14 (+0.66 +6.75)
	\geq 1000 m asl	0.46 (0.16 0.73)	+0.76 (+0.13 +2.43)

4.2 Frost

Figure 10 describes the development of the projected number of frost days, which are defined as days when the minimum air temperature falls below 0°C . For both RCPs, there is a significant decrease in the number of frost days across both elevation bands.

This observed reduction in the number of frost days aligns with broader climate change projections, suggesting a warming trend in which temperatures are less likely to fall below freezing. Furthermore, when comparing this annual trend in frost days with the number of frost days during the vegetation period (Figure 11), the information indicates that only a small fraction of frost days occurs during this critical period. In this context, the lack of a significant trend in frost days during the vegetation period implies that the potential impact on plant life and agricultural activities related to frost during the growing season may not be as pronounced as the overall reduction in frost days might suggest.

Figure 10: Annual number of frost days ($T_{min} < 0^{\circ}\text{C}$) in the Ötscher Region for the ÖKS 15 regional climate scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5. Left column of sub-figures shows time-series of smoothed ensemble statistics (median, 10th and 90th percentile), right column shows the ensemble distribution of mean values over two different periods. Values are reported for two elevation ranges.

Figure 11: Annual number of frost days in the vegetation period in the Ötscher Region for the ÖKS 15 regional climate scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5. Left column of sub-figures shows time-series of smoothed ensemble statistics (median, 10th and 90th percentile), right column shows the ensemble distribution of mean values over two different periods. Values are reported for two elevation ranges.

Table 4.2: Median (min | max) values of ÖKS15 model ensemble for annual number of frost days ($T_{min} < 0^{\circ}\text{C}$) in the vegetation period over the period 1991-2020 and the change signal in the period 2021-2050 over two elevation ranges

RCP	elevation	1991-2020	Δ in 2021-2050
RCP2.6	< 1000 m asl	3.91 (3.60 4.61)	-0.13 (-1.1 +1.64)
	\geq 1000 m asl	3.03 (2.52 4.53)	+0.1 (-1.25 +1.33)
RCP8.5	< 1000 m asl	4.13 (2.23 5.30)	-0.7 (-2.71 +1.65)
	\geq 1000 m asl	2.83 (1.82 5.23)	-0.07 (-1.41 +1.04)

4.3 Severe and Extreme Precipitation Events

The classification of precipitation intensities is based on the observed distribution of daily precipitation rates from 1991-2020. Precipitation events are categorized as "severe" if the rates fall within the 95th and 98th percentile, and as "extreme" if they exceed the 98th percentile. The projections indicate an anticipated increase in severe and extreme precipitation, though with notable variability between ensemble members, highlighting the inherent uncertainty in these predictions. Median values of the anticipated change range from +9.9% for RCP8.5 and +15.5% for RCP2.6 for severe precipitation intensities, and between +13.6 (RCP8.5) to +20.2% (RCP2.6) for extreme events. These values provide a central estimate of the projected changes, indicating a general trend of increased precipitation intensity under both emission scenarios. However, it's crucial to acknowledge the large ensemble spread in precipitation-related indicators, which introduces uncertainty to the findings. The variability between different ensemble members emphasizes the complex and uncertain nature of predicting precipitation changes in a future climate. Factors such as regional variations, complex atmospheric dynamics, and model uncertainties contribute to this variability.

Figure 12: Number of days with sever precipitation in the Ötscher Region for the ÖKS 15 regional climate scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5. Left column of sub-figures shows time-series of smoothed ensemble statistics (median, 10th and 90th percentile), right column shows the ensemble distribution of mean values over two different periods. Values are reported for two elevation ranges.

Table 4.3: Median (min | max) values of ÖKS15 model ensemble for annual number of days with severe precipitation over the period 1991-2020 and the change signal in the period 2021-2050 over two elevation ranges

RCP	elevation	1991-2020	Δ in 2021-2050
RCP2.6	< 1000 m asl	4.86 (4.70 5.10)	+0.75 (-0.7 +1.2)
	≥ 1000 m asl	5.02 (4.86 5.27)	+0.78 (-0.74 +1.26)
RCP8.5	< 1000 m asl	4.87 (4.46 5.01)	+0.48 (-0.28 +1.78)
	≥ 1000 m asl	5.03 (4.59 5.16)	+0.61 (-0.42 +2.03)

Table 4.4: Median (min | max) values of ÖKS15 model ensemble for annual number of days with extreme precipitation over the period 1991-2020 and the change signal in the period 2021-2050 over two elevation ranges

RCP	elevation	1991-2020	Δ in 2021-2050
RCP2.6	< 1000 m asl	3.26 (3.15 3.42)	+0.57 (+0.07 +1.2)
	\geq 1000 m asl	3.36 (3.26 3.53)	+0.68 (-0.22 +1.28)
RCP8.5	< 1000 m asl	3.26 (2.99 3.35)	+0.52 (-0.44 +1.2)
	\geq 1000 m asl	3.37 (3.08 3.46)	+0.42 (-0.53 +1.09)

4.4 Snow

Natural Snowcover

The mean annual snow depth, as depicted in Figure 13 and summarized in Table 4.5, shows no clear trend up to 2050. Instead, there is a notable high interannual variability and considerable ensemble spread.

Regarding the snow season length (Figure 14 and Table 4.6), a slight decrease is projected for both RCPs. The snow season length is expressed as the number of days with a snow cover of at least 10cm. Median values of the change signal indicate a decrease in snow season length, with values ranging from -3.4 days for RCP 2.6 to -8.6 days for RCP 8.5 for elevations under 1000 m a.s.l. Above 1000 m a.s.l, median values range from -4.8 days for RCP 2.6 to -10.7 days for RCP 8.5. However, it is emphasized that individual climate models do not consistently agree on the direction of change for the snow season length, highlighting the uncertainty in predicting this indicator.

Figure 13: Mean annual snow depth for the Ötscher Region for the ÖKS 15 regional climate scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5. Left column of sub-figures shows time-series of smoothed ensemble statistics (median, 10th and 90th percentile), right column shows the ensemble distribution of mean values over two different periods. Values are reported for two elevation ranges.

Table 4.5: Median (min | max) values of ÖKS15 model ensemble for mean snow depth (cm) over the period 1991-2020 and the change signal in the period 2021-2050 over two elevation ranges.

RCP	elevation	1991-2020	Δ in 2021-2050
RCP2.6	< 1000 m asl	29.27 (26.18 34.08)	+2.51 (-10.33 +7.69)
	≥ 1000 m asl	52.62 (44.58 57.66)	+3.12 (-17.41 +12.25)
RCP8.5	< 1000 m asl	26.92 (20.41 38.10)	-2.62 (-7.63 +3.44)
	≥ 1000 m asl	46.67 (37.46 63.01)	-2.63 (-11.38 +5.15)

Figure 14: Annual snow season length (as number of days with snow depth $\geq 10\text{cm}$) for the Ötscher Region for the ÖKS 15 regional climate scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5. Left column of sub-figures shows time-series of smoothed ensemble statistics (median, 10th and 90th percentile), right column shows the ensemble distribution of mean values over two different periods. Values are reported for two elevation ranges

Table 4.6: Median (min | max) values of ÖKS15 model ensemble for number of days with snow depth $\geq 10\text{cm}$ (days) over the period 1991-2020 and the change signal in the period 2021-2050 over two elevation ranges.

RCP	elevation	1991-2020	Δ in 2021-2050
RCP2.6	< 1000 m asl	132.72 (121.29 138.96)	-3.35 (-38.06 +8.45)
	≥ 1000 m asl	167.15 (150.72 174.24)	-4.76 (-35.1 +5.41)
RCP8.5	< 1000 m asl	123.28 (110.31 139.53)	-8.64 (-22.02 +1.14)
	≥ 1000 m asl	159.40 (144.00 175.44)	-10.73 (-22.03 +1.6)

Technical Snow Production

Technical snow production is a common practice in many ski resorts across the alpine region, including the Ötscher region where the Lackenhof ski resort utilizes snow guns and lances to maintain optimal skiing conditions. The effectiveness of technical snow production is contingent upon ambient atmospheric conditions, particularly the wet-bulb temperature. Colder wet-bulb temperatures during production contribute to higher-quality snow and reduced water consumption.

In this analysis, a threshold of -4°C is employed to identify suitable snowmaking hours within the months of November to January. The climate projections indicate an expected decrease in the number of snowmaking hours across both RCPs and elevation ranges.

However, on average, from 2021 to 2050, there are still approximately 25 days within this period where atmospheric conditions are conducive to snowmaking, even in the lower elevation band.

Therefore, the analysis suggests that even under 1300m, technical snow production remains viable, on average, during the specified period. This information is crucial for ski resorts in planning and adapting their snow management strategies in response to anticipated climate changes, ensuring sustainable snow conditions for recreational activities.

Figure 15: Number of snowmaking hours (number of hours where technical snow production is possible) November to January in the Ötscher Region for the ÖKS 15 regional climate scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5. Time-series show smoothed ensemble statistics (median, 10th and 90th percentile). Values are reported for two elevation ranges.

Table 4.7: Median (min | max) values of ÖKS15 model ensemble for number of hours available for technical snow production ($T_w \leq -4^\circ\text{C}$) over the period 1991-2020 and the change signal in the period 2021-2050 over two elevation ranges.

RCP	elevation	1991-2020	Δ in 2021-2050
RCP2.6	800-1300 m	807 (761 842)	-176 (-233 -17)
	1300-1800 m	943 (914 990)	-71 (-178 -4)
RCP8.5	800-1300 m	798 (730 862)	-130 (-213 -6)
	1300-1800 m	939 (882 1012)	-134 (-214 +10)

4.5 Drought

The projected number of consecutive dry days per year is expected to remain stable compared to the baseline period. No significant trend is identified, taking into account the ensemble spread.

Figure 16: Annual number of consecutive dry days for the Ötscher Region for the ÖKS 15 regional climate scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5. Left column of sub-figures shows time-series of smoothed ensemble statistics (median, 10th and 90th percentile), right column shows the ensemble distribution of mean values over two different periods. Values are reported for two elevation ranges.

Table 4.8: Median (min | max) values of ÖKS15 model ensemble for number of consecutive dry days over the period 1991-2020 and the change signal in the period 2021-2050 over two elevation ranges.

RCP	elevation	1991-2020	Δ in 2021-2050
RCP2.6	< 1000 m asl	108.54 (98.18 115.22)	+0.25 (-6.01 +13.55)
	\geq 1000 m asl	103.30 (93.24 109.68)	-0.55 (-5.92 +13.71)
RCP8.5	< 1000 m asl	105.18 (98.14 127.30)	-1.68 (-11.93 +10.5)
	\geq 1000 m asl	99.42 (93.47 122.61)	-1.4 (-10.75 +10.52)

4.6 Vegetation

The onset of the annual growing season/vegetation period is defined as the first calendar day of a consecutive series of days, during which the average daily air temperature is at least 5°C. Additionally, this period must extend for at least six days and surpass the subsequent phase characterized by average daily air temperatures below 5°C.

Analysis of Figure 17 and Figure 18 reveals that, on average, the duration of the vegetation period is projected to increase, with an earlier onset in the year. When comparing the period 2021-2050 with the baseline period of 1991-2020, there is a median lengthening of the vegetation period by approximately +8 days for regions under 1000 m. This alteration may have implications for agriculture and forestry practices. The data does not indicate an increase in frost occurrences during the lengthened vegetation period, as illustrated in Figure 11.

Figure 17: Julian day of the start of the growing season for the Ötscher Region for the ÖKS 15 regional climate scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5. Left column of sub-figures shows time-series of smoothed ensemble statistics (median, 10th and 90th percentile), right column shows the ensemble distribution of mean values over two different periods. Values are reported for two elevation ranges.

Figure 18: Annual length of the growing season in days for the Ötscher Region for the ÖKS 15 regional climate scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5. Left column of sub-figures shows time-series of smoothed ensemble statistics (median, 10th and 90th percentile), right column shows the ensemble distribution of mean values over two different periods. Values are reported for two elevation ranges.

Table 4.9: Median (min | max) values of ÖKS15 model ensemble for the the start of the growing season (Julian day) over the period 1991-2020 and the change signal in the period 2021-2050 over two elevation ranges.

RCP	elevation	1991-2020	Δ in 2021-2050
RCP2.6	< 1000 m asl	101.95 (96.70 103.78)	-3.6 (-6.17 +0.13)
	≥ 1000 m asl	114.43 (110.02 118.34)	-4.01 (-6.98 +0.38)
RCP8.5	< 1000 m asl	100.79 (96.17 104.08)	-3.98 (-7.13 +1.4)
	≥ 1000 m asl	115.32 (109.02 118.65)	-4.94 (-8.56 +0.07)

Table 4.10: Median (min | max) values of ÖKS15 model ensemble for growing season length (days) over the period 1991-2020 and the change signal in the period 2021-2050 over two elevation ranges.

RCP	elevation	1991-2020	Δ in 2021-2050
RCP2.6	< 1000 m asl	190.70 (183.85 192.07)	+8.06 (+6.19 +10.7)
	≥ 1000 m asl	169.21 (159.80 172.79)	+9.34 (+4.83 +11.91)
RCP8.5	< 1000 m asl	188.83 (185.62 196.98)	+8.33 (+2.95 +15.93)
	≥ 1000 m asl	166.81 (161.75 176.68)	+9.77 (+4.29 +18.81)

4.7 Hiking Days

The projected annual count of dry hiking days, defined as days with negligible precipitation amount and maximum air temperatures between 15°C and 25°C, is anticipated to remain relatively stable. This assessment takes into account the substantial variability among different climate models, as depicted in Figure 19 and summarized in Table 4.11.

Figure 19: Annual number of dry hiking days ($15\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \leq T_{max} \leq 25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $P \leq 1\text{ mm}$) for the Ötscher Region for the ÖKS 15 regional climate scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5. Left column of sub-figures shows time-series of smoothed ensemble statistics (median, 10th and 90th percentile), right column shows the ensemble distribution of mean values over two different periods. Values are reported for two elevation ranges.

Table 4.11: Median (min | max) values of ÖKS15 model ensemble for number of dry hiking days over the period 1991-2020 and the change signal in the period 2021-2050 over two elevation ranges.

RCP	elevation	1991-2020	Δ in 2021-2050
RCP2.6	< 1000 m asl	74.37 (68.03 79.77)	+3.01 (-3.93 +6.26)
	≥ 1000 m asl	67.90 (62.95 70.43)	+2.92 (-0.77 +8.64)
RCP8.5	< 1000 m asl	73.94 (69.43 78.62)	-0.5 (-5.44 +5.95)
	≥ 1000 m asl	66.96 (61.46 74.86)	+2.86 (-7.87 +10.74)

5 Vulnerability to Climate Change

This analysis examines changes in key climate parameters, specifically air temperature and precipitation, along with associated climate indicators, between a baseline period (1991-2020) and a near-future period (2021-2050). The objective is to explore how the projected alterations in the current climate will impact various aspects of nature and society in the Ötscher region within a manageable timeframe.

However, it is crucial to acknowledge that, even though this study focuses on imminent changes between what has been experienced in the last decades and what is projected for the coming decades, it is essential to view this within the broader context of anticipated climate change. The baseline climate period (1991-2020) has already undergone considerable changes compared to previous periods, as illustrated in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Mean annual air temperatures for five 30-year periods. The Boxplots display the spread of the model ensembles for RCP2.6 and RCP8.5.

The period from 1971-2000 was approximately 0.4°C and 0.6°C cooler than 1991-2020 (median values for RCP2.6 and RCP8.5). This difference is just below the projected change anticipated for 2021-2050 (+0.6°C for RCP2.6 and +0.8°C for RCP8.5, as detailed in Table 3.1). Depending on the RCP, this change is expected to persist until the end of the century, with projections ranging from +0.8°C for RCP2.6 to +3.2°C for RCP8.5. Therefore, while the climate change signal might be somewhat limited for the near-future period, understanding this context is crucial. Especially, for long-term planning sectors such as forestry.

Agriculture and Forestry

Anticipated climate change is projected to lead to small extension of the growing season length and an earlier onset in the near future. Damages to forests from bark beetle infestations are more likely to occur in a warmer climate, as rising damage numbers have shown in the last years (Hoch and Steyrer, 2020).

Tourism

Anticipated climate changes, particularly in cities, suggest a continual increase in summer temperatures and hot days. In the Ötscher region, this phenomenon might positively impact the development of summer tourism. The region's appeal for summer vacations is enhanced by the cooling effect of the forest cover and the opportunity to explore higher elevations during warm days.

Conversely, winter tourism, dependent on snow conditions, will likely face challenges similar to those experienced in recent years. While snowmaking remains a viable option, the time windows for such practices are expected to shorten. Looking further into the future (2071-2100), natural snow season length is projected to decrease significantly, contingent on the RCP. The average season length is anticipated to shorten by 74 days for RCP8.5 and 13 days for RCP2.6. These projections highlight potential shifts in the winter tourism landscape, emphasizing the importance of adapting to evolving climate conditions for sustainable tourism planning.

Extreme Precipitation Events

Precipitation intensities that are considered severe or extreme from current observations, are projected to increase in the coming decades in the ÖKS15 scenarios (with high uncertainties). Although, natural variability of extreme events are larger than changes due to climate change. This might have implications for flood and landslide occurrence and related planning of protection measures.

The current analysis does not indicate an imminent shock resulting from climate change comparing climate periods 1991-2020 and 2021-2050. However, this assertion may not hold true in scenarios characterized by minimal reductions in greenhouse gases and sustained warming, such as the RCP8.5 pathway, especially when considering longer time frames. In such circumstances, severe consequences are likely to emerge.

6 References

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7 Appendix

Indicator (German)	Indicator (Englisch)	Details
Mittlere Lufttemperatur (°C)	Mean Air Temperature (°C)	$(T_{min}+T_{max})/2$
Anzahl der Hitzetage	Number of Hot Days	$T_{max} \geq 30 \text{ °C}$
Anzahl der Frosttage	Number of Frost Days	$T_{min} < 0 \text{ °C}$
Beginn der Vegetationsperiode	Start of Growing Season (Julian Day)	Als Beginn der jährlichen Vegetationszeit/Vegetationsperiode gilt der erste Kalendertag einer mehrtägigen Abfolge mit einer mittleren täglichen Lufttemperatur von mindestens (\geq) 5°C, wenn sich diese Periode über zumindest sechs Tage erstreckt und länger ist als die nachfolgende Periode an Tagen mit einer mittleren täglichen Lufttemperatur unter 5°C
Länge der Vegetationsperiode	Growing Season Length (d)	Anzahl der Tage zwischen Beginn und Ende der Vegetationsperiode, basierend auf die oben genannte Definition.
Niederschlagsmenge (mm)	Precipitation Amount (mm)	$\sum pr$
Anzahl der Tage in Trockenepisoden	Number of Consecutive Dry Days	$pr \text{ pro Tag} < 1 \text{ mm für mind. 5 Tage}$
Anzahl der Tage mit schwerem Niederschlag	Number of Days with Severe Precipitation on Wet Days	$\sum \text{Tage mit } pct_{95} \leq pr < pct_{98} \text{ (pct aus 1991-2020)}$
Anzahl der Tage mit extremem Niederschlag	Number of Days with Extreme Precipitation on Wet Days	$\sum \text{Tage mit } pct_{98} \leq pr \text{ (pct aus 1991-2020)}$

Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index	Standardized Precipitation Evaporation Index	pr - potenzielle Verdunstung
Anzahl der trockenen Wandertage	Number of Dry Hiking Days	Anzahl der Tage wo $15\text{ °C} \leq T_{\text{max}} \leq 25\text{ °C}$ und $pr \leq 1\text{ mm}$
Tage mit Schneedecke $\geq 10\text{ cm}$	Number of Days with Snow Depth $\geq 10\text{cm}$	Anzahl der Tage mit Schneehöhe $\geq 10\text{cm}$
Mittlere Schneehöhe (cm)	Mean Snow Depth (cm)	mittlere Schneehöhe
Maximale tägliche Neuschneemenge (cm)	Maximum of Daily New Snow (cm)	$\max(\sum \text{snow1Day})$